

Antibiogram Profiles of *Salmonella Typhi* Isolated from Typhoid Fever Patients in Akure, Nigeria and Effects of Some Herbal Concoctions on Antibiotic Resistant Strains

Itanrin, Oluwadamilola Ayomide* and Adebolu, Tinuola Tokunbo

Department of Microbiology, Federal University of Technology, PMB 704, Akure, Ondo State,
Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: itanrin1999@gmail.com; +2348105878908

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164180>

Abstract

Typhoid fever also known as enteric fever is a severe multisystemic disease caused by *Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi*. Although, the infection could be life threatening however prompt treatment with effective antibiotics can lead to quick recovery of infected individuals. However, with the increase in the number of antibiotic-resistant bacterial species, it becomes imperative to assess the antibiogram profiles of *S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi* isolated from typhoid patients in the studied community and to also search for more effective therapies. This study therefore was aimed at evaluating the antibiogram profiles of some clinical isolates of *Salmonella* species (n = 17) from the blood samples of patients positive to Widal test at a selected Government Hospital in Akure and to also evaluate three local herbal concoctions (HCs) for antibacterial activity against the isolated *Salmonella* species. Standard methods were used for both the assessment of the antibiogram profiles of the isolated *Salmonella* species and the evaluation of the antibacterial activity of HCs against the isolated *Salmonella* species. The antibiogram profile of the isolated *Salmonella* species revealed that all the isolates were resistant to Augmentin (100%), Chloramphenicol (100%) and Streptomycin (100%). The HCs however exerted superior growth inhibition of the isolated *Salmonella* species. This study shows that the HCs evaluated in this study exerted potent antibacterial activity against the isolated *Salmonella* species. Therefore, the studied HCs could be explored to produce novel drugs for the treatment of typhoid fever.

Keywords: *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, Antibiogram, Typhoid Fever, Herbal Concoctions

INTRODUCTION

Typhoid fever (Iba Jefun jedi) also known as enteric fever is a severe multisystemic diseases which is caused by *Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi* bacteria through ingestion of contaminated foods and water (ECDC, 2023). Salmonellae are short, Gram negative, facultative anaerobic, rod-shaped bacteria (Hamza, 2022). Typhoid fever poses a global threat especially in developing countries and underdeveloped countries in Africa, Mediterranean seas, Southeast Asia and Western Pacific regions (WHO, 2023). Although the infection could be life threatening, prompt treatment with effective antibiotics however can lead to quick recovery of infected individuals (Mokhesi and

Modjadji, 2022). However, due to the rise of treatment failure lately because of the challenge of antibiotic resistance leading to the development of multidrug resistant strains of *Salmonella typhi* and *S. paratyphi* and lack of quick access to conventional medicine, it has resulted in the use of herbal concoctions based on oral traditions most especially in rural areas to treat the infection. Interestingly, the use of some of these herbal concoctions mitigate the infection however, there is no scientific explanation (Oladunjoye *et al.*, 2022). This study therefore was carried out to evaluate the antibiogram profile of *Salmonella* species isolated from cases of typhoid fever and to determine the effectiveness of some local herbal concoctions (HCs) that are used in Akure metropolis for possible antibacterial activity against these bacterial species in the search for more effective treatment of typhoid.

METHODOLOGY

Prior the commencement of the study, ethical approval was gotten from the Ondo State Health Research Ethics Committee (OSHREC 26/02/2024/632). Blood samples (5ml) were collected from Widal test positive patients (n=17 in which “n” is number of samples collected) at selected government hospitals in Akure into EDTA bottles and it was transported to the Post Graduate Research Laboratory, Microbiology Department, FUTA, Akure, Nigeria in ice coolers for culturing, isolation and identification using standard microbiological techniques. Molecular characterization of the isolated *Salmonella* species was carried out after the extraction of their DNA using standard protocol. The plant materials for the preparation of the herbal concoctions were bought from 3 different herb’s sellers in Akure, Nigeria. The compositions of the three concoctions are shown in Table 1 (C1= Concoction 1, C2= Concoction 2, C3= Concoction 3, += Present, - = Absent).

Table 1: Components of Herbal Concoctions evaluated with their Local, English and Scientific names

S/N	Local Name	English name	Scientific name	Category	C 1	C 2	C 3
1	Egbo tude	Loose bondage root	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> (Benth.)	Root	+	-	-
2	Ako ogun	False rubber tree	<i>Aristolochia ringens</i> Lam.	Root	+	-	-
3	Epo cocoa	Cocoa tree	<i>Theobroma cacao</i> (Benth.)	Bark	+	-	+
4	Epo Afara	Africa limba wood, frake	<i>Terminalia superba</i> L.	Bark	+	+	-
5	Epo agbon	Coconut	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> (L.)	Bark	+	-	-
6	Poroporo	Sorghum leaf stem	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> L. moenth	Leaves & Stem	+	+	+
7	Alubosa ayu	Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Seed	+	-	-
8	Iyere	Uziza seed/ West african pepper	<i>Piper guineense</i> Schumach & Thonn; C.	Seed	+	-	-
9	Saka	Chia seeds	<i>Salvia hispanica</i> L.	Seed	+	-	-
10	Epo oruwo	Brimstone tree	<i>Morinda lucida</i> (Benth.)	Bark	+	-	-
11	Abere	Abeere aigulle	<i>Huntaria umbellate</i> (L.)	Seed	+	-	-
12	Ariwo	African nutmeg	<i>Monodora myristica</i> (Dunal.)	Bark	+	-	-
13	Eru Alamo	Black pepper	<i>Piper nigrum</i> (Dunal.)	Seed	+	-	-

14	Epo igi eje	Blood tree	<i>Justicia carne</i>	Bark	+	-	-
15	Epo mangoro	Mango tree	<i>Mangnifera indica</i> (L.)	Bark	+	+	-
16	Epo ikún	Ginseng	<i>Desmodium adscendens</i> (L.)	Bark	+	-	-
17	Boni	Boni fruit/ Chinese laurel fruit	<i>Antidesma bunius</i> (L.)	Seed	+	-	+
18	Epo ahun	Stool wood, pattern wood	<i>Alstonia boonei</i> (Benth.)	Bark	+	+	+
19	Obi	Kolanut	<i>Cola nitida</i> (T.)	Seed	+	-	-
20	Aidan onigumerin	Aiden fruits	<i>Tetrapleura tetraptera</i> (L.)	Fruit	+	-	-
21	Jedi bomubomu	Rubber tree	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (R.B.)	Bark	+	-	-
22	Ewe laali	Henna leaves	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> (L.)	Leaves	+	-	-
23	Egbo dongoyaro	Neem tree	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Benth)	Bark	+	+	-
24	Ewe oruwo	Brimstone tree	<i>Morinda lucida</i> (L.)	Leaves	+	-	-
25	Okuku	Castor seeds	<i>Pteleiopsis suberosa</i> Engl &Diels; T	Seed	+	-	-
26	Ewe Akoko	African border tree	<i>Newbouldia laevis</i> (P.Beauv) Seem.	Leaves	-	+	-
27	Ewe tea	Lemon grass	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	+	+
28	Ewe dongoyaro	Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Benth)	Leaves	-	+	-
29	Ewe gurofa	Guava leaf	<i>Psidium guajava</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	+	+
30	Awopa	African yellow wood	<i>Enantia chlorantiam</i> Oliv.	Bark	-	+	-
31	Egbo ijebo	Mahogany tree	<i>Entandrophragma angolense</i> (T.)	Bark	-	+	+
32	Ego Opotó	Ficus tree/Broom cluster fig	Ficus tree/Broom cluster fig	Bark	-	+	-
33	Ewe mangoro	Mango	<i>Mangnifera indica</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	+	+
34	Egbo gberesi	Yellow cheesewood	<i>Nauclea orientalis</i> (Benth.)	Bark	-	-	+
35	Ewe oparun	Bamboo leaves	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> (Schrad.)	Leaves	-	-	+
36	Ewe kaaju	Cashew leaves	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	-	+
37	Ewe ahun	Stool wood, pattern wood leaves	<i>Alstonia boonei</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	-	+
38	Ewe amuje	Crimson thyme leaves	<i>Byrsocarpus coccinus</i> Benth.	Leaves	-	-	+
39	Ewe rumuarugbo	Mountain thistle leaves	<i>Acanthus montanus</i> (Nees)	Leaves	-	-	+
40	Ewe pear	Pear leaves	<i>Pyrus communis</i> (L.)	Leaves	-	-	+
41	Ewe osunpupa	Pasture weed	<i>Cyathula achyranthoides</i> (Kunth)	Leaves	-	-	+

42	Epo afara	Afara, Africa limba wood, frake	<i>Terminalia superba</i> (L.)	Bark	-	-	+
43	Irinje	Croton seeds	<i>Croton tiglium</i> (S.)	Seed	-	-	+

Key: C1 = Concoction 1; C2 = Concoction 2; C3 = Concoction 3

The components for the herbal concoctions were rinsed properly with potable water and put into three separate pots. Five liters of potable water was introduced into the first pot (Concoction 1) and 3L each was put in the two other pots for the preparation of concoctions 2 and 3 respectively. The concoctions were cooked for 45 minutes according to the herb seller's instructions based on oral tradition and allowed to cool down before usage. The antibiogram of the isolated *Salmonella* species was done using Kirby Bauer's diffusion method according to Hudzicki (2009) while the growth inhibitory assay of HCs on the isolated *Salmonella* was carried out using agar-well diffusion assay on Mueller Hilton agar. Prior the growth inhibitory assay, the prepared concoctions were first purified using milipore filter (0.45 to 1.0µl) according to Zhang *et al.* (2021). Ciprofloxacin (30µg) (The most effective antibiotic from the antibiogram profile of the isolated *Salmonella* species) and Chloramphenicol (30µg) (the least effective antibiotic) were used as positive control while sterile distilled water was used as the negative control. The plates were incubated without inversion at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the zone of inhibition was recorded. The Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and the Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of concoction C1 (which is the concoction that exerted the highest growth inhibition on the isolated *Salmonella* species) were determined using standard microbiological techniques. The quantitative phytochemical analyses of concoction C1 was carried out according to Osuagwu *et al.* (2021). Data were statistically analysed using one-way ANOVA and treatment means separated using Duncan's new multiple range test at 5% level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The antibiogram profiles of the isolated *Salmonella* species showed that all of the isolates were 100% resistant to Augmentin, Streptomycin and Chloramphenicol while 94.1% were resistant to Amoxicillin and Seprin respectively. However, 58.2% of the isolated *Salmonella* were susceptible to Ofloxacin and 52.9% to Ciprofloxacin (Table 2). This observation is similar to the findings of Sajib *et al.* (2023). The relative percentage inhibition of the isolated *Salmonella* species observed with Ofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin shows that only the antibiotics belonging to the Fluoroquinolone group (Ofloxacin, Ciprofloxacin and Pefloxacin) are effective in inhibiting the growth of the bacteria. Fluoroquinolones achieve high concentrations in key infection sites like the bile, bowel, and within macrophages, where *Salmonella* resides, making them clinically superior for treating enteric fever compared to older first-line antibiotics (like chloramphenicol, ampicillin, and co-trimoxazole).

Although the evaluated HCs did not inhibit the growth of the isolated *Salmonella* sp. on agar plate when used immediately after preparation however by the 10th day of preparation, they were observed to exert superior growth inhibition of the isolated *Salmonella* sp. than most of the antibiotics used (Table 3). That is, the older the concoction is, the more effective it became in inhibiting the growth of the isolated *Salmonella* sp. on agar plate. This is in agreement with the observation of Maina *et al.* (2024) that it takes time for the phytochemicals in herbal concoctions to leach out into the medium in which they are soaked. The growth inhibitory activity of the concoction however in this study was observed to decline by day 25 post preparation. The MIC of concoction C1 on *Salmonella* species was observed to be 75% (volume) while the MBC was 100% (volume). The high MIC and MBC values showed that high concentrations of the concoction C1 is required to inhibit and kill the

organism. This agrees with the report of Balaaji *et al.* (2021). According to their study, higher concentration of extracts are needed to inhibit and kill *S. typhi* than conventional antibiotics.

The quantitative phytochemical profile of concoction C1 showed the presence of Saponins, Tannins, Terpenoids, Cardiac glycosides, Flavonoids and Phenols while Alkaloid was found to be absent (Table 4). This contradicts the report of Missa *et al.* (2015) that alkaloids are always found to be present in herbal mixtures. Out of the phytochemicals observed in C1, phenols was observed to have the highest concentration while terpenes had the lowest concentration. This agrees with the report of Tepal (2016). The high phenolic content indicates that C1 has strong antioxidant potential. Phenols are known to have the ability to neutralize free radicals and stop oxidative damage which is advantageous for maintaining good health and prevention of diseases.

Table 2: Antibiogram profiles of the isolated *Salmonella* species

ISOLATES	CPX	AM	AU	CN	PEF	OFX	S	SXT	CH	SP
	S ≥21	S ≥22	S ≥18	S ≥15	S ≥16	S ≥16	S ≥15	S ≥16	S ≥18	S ≥17
	I- 16-20	I- 16-20	I- 14-17	I- 13-14	I- 13-15	I-13- 1-5	I- 11-15	I- 13-17	I-14-16	
	R≤15	R≤14	R≤13	R≤12	R≤12	R ≤12	R≤11	R≤10	R≤12	R<13
ARA1	21.01 ±0.00 ^b	0.01±0.0 0 _{g,h}	0.01± 0.01 ^{fg} _{,h}	17.02 ±0.01 ^d	15.01 ±0.00 ^e	25.01 ±0.00 ^b	0.01±0. 01 ^h	0.02±0. 01 _{f,g}	0.01±0. 00 _f	18.02±0.01 ^a
ARA2	22.02± 0.00 ^a	0.01±0.0 1 _g	0.02± 0.01 ^s _{,h}	18.02 ±0.00 ^c	17.02 ±0.01 ^c _{,d}	20.02 ±0.00 ^d	0.02±0. 01 _f	0.01±0. 01 _g	0.02±0. 00 _g	15.02±0.00 ^e
ARA5	0.02±0. 00 _a	0.02±0.0 0 _a	0.02± 0.01 ^a	0.01± 0.01 ^b	0.01± 0.00 _{b,c}	0.02± 0.00 ^a	0.01±0. 01 _b	0.02±0. 01 _a	0.02±0. 00 _a	0.01±0.01 ^c
ARA6	23.02± 0.00 _{a,b}	24.01±0. 02 _a	15.02 ±0.01 _d	17.02 ±0.00 ^c _{,d}	19.02 ±0.00 ^c	20.02 ±0.00 ^b _{,c}	0.02±0. 01 _e	0.01±0. 01 _e	0.02±0. 00 _e	15.02±0.00 ^d
ARA7	0.02±0. 00 _a	0.02±0.0 0 _a	0.02± 0.01 ^a	0.01± 0.01 ^a	0.01± 0.00 ^b	0.02± 0.00 ^b	0.01±0. 01 _a	0.02±0. 01 _a	0.02±0. 00 _a	0.01±0.01 ^b
ARA8	10.02± 0.00 ^c	0.02±0.0 0 _d	12.01 ±0.01 _b	17.01 ±0.01 ^a	0.01± 0.01 _{b,c}	0.02± 0.00 ^d	0.02±0. 00 _d	0.01±0. 00 _e	0.01±0. 00 _e	0.01±0.01 ^d _e
ARA9	20.01± 0.00 ^c	0.02±0.0 1 _f	12.02 ±0.00 ^b	15.02 ±0.00 ^c	13.00 ±0.00 ^d	18.01 ±0.01 ^b	12.01± 0.01 ^c	0.00±0. 00 _g	0.02±0. 00 _f	0.01±0.01 ^f
ARA10	11.01± 0.00 ^c	0.01±0.0 1 _c	0.01± 0.00 ^c	0.02± 0.00 ^b	0.02 ^b ±0.01 ^b	0.01± 0.00 _{b,c}	0.02±0. 00 _{b,c}	0.01±0. 01 _b	0.01±0. 00 _b	0.02±0.01 ^b _c
UTH1	19.01± 0.01 ^a	0.00±0.0 1 _e	0.01± 0.01 ^d	0.02± 0.00 ^a	10.02 ±0.01 ^c	13.01 ±0.01 ^b	0.02±0. 00 _d	0.02±0. 01 _d	0.02±0. 01 _d	0.02±0.01 ^d
UTH2	22.01± 0.01 ^a	0.01±0.0 1 _g	16.01 ±0.00 _d	13.01 ±0.00 ^c	19.01 ±0.01 ^c	20.02 ±0.01 ^b	10.02± 0.00 ^f	19.01± 0.00 ^c	10.02± 0.00 ^f	13.01±0.01 ^d
UTH3	13.01± 0.00 ^c	0.02±0.0 1 _c	10.02 ±0.00 _b	0.00± 0.00 ^a	0.02± 0.01 ^c	0.01± 0.01 ^c	0.02±0. 01 _c	0.01±0. 01 _c	0.01±0. 01 _c	0.02±0.01 ^c

UTH4	10.01± 0.01 ^a	0.02±0.0 1 ^c	0.01± 0.01 ^b	0.01± 0.00 ^b	0.01± 0.01 ^b	0.02± 0.00 ^b	0.02±0. 01 ^b	0.01±0. 01 ^b	0.01±0. 00 ^b	0.01±0.01 ^b
UTH5	25.02± 0.00 ^b	0.02±0.0 1 ^b	0.01± 0.01 ^f	17.02 ±0.00 ^d	20.02 ±0.00 ^c	22.02 ±0.00 ^b	0.01±0. 01 ^f	0.02±0. 01 ^f	0.02±0. 01 ^f	16.02±0.01 ^c
ARA2A	27.01± 0.01 ^a	0.02±0.0 0 ^f	0.02± 0.01 ^f	16.02 ±0.01 ^d	22.02 ±0.00 ^c	25.02 ±0.00 ^b	0.01±0. 01 ^f	0.02±0. 01 ^f	0.02±0. 01 ^f	14 01±0.01 ^f
ARA2B	26.01± 0.01 ^a	0.02±0.0 0 ^f	0.02± 0.01 ^f	14.02 ±0.00 ^b	18.02 ±0.00 ^c	21.02 ±0.00 ^b	0.02±0. 00 ^f	0.01±0. 00 ^g	0.02±0. 00 ^f	16.02±0.01 ^f
ARA2C	24.02± 0.00 ^b	0.02±0.0 0 ^e	0.01± 0.01 ^c	10.02 ±0.00 ^d	17.02 ±0.00 ^c	20.01 ±0.01 ^b	0.02±0. 01 ^e	0.02±0. 01 ^e	0.02±0. 00 ^e	17.02±0.00 ^c
ARA2D		24.02± 0.01±	0.02±0.01 ^s 0.02±	15.02 12.01±	17.02 0.01 ^a	18.01 ±0.01 ^e	21.02 ±0.00 ^d	0.01± ±0.01 ^c		
			0.00 ^g	0.00 ^s	0.00 ^s	0.01 ^f				
Percentage susceptibility (%)	52.9/47	5.9/94.1	0.0/10	47.1/5	47.1/5	58.8/4	0.0/100	5.9/94.	0.0/100	11.8/88.2
Resistivity (%)	.1		0.0	2.9	2.9	1.2	.0	1		

Key: CPX-Ciprofloxacin, AU-Augmentin, AM-Amoxycillin, CN-Gentamycin, PEF-Perfloxacin, OFX-Ofloxacin, S- Streptomycin, SXT- Septrin, CH-Chloramphenicol, SP-Sparfloxacin ; Values interpreted according to CLSI (2020). Values with different superscripts in the row are statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 3: Growth inhibitory activity of the prepared herbal concoctions at different post – preparation days against the isolated *Salmonella* species. Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)/Post-preparation day(d)

	10	20	25	30
Treatment				
C1	13.04 ± 2.12 ^a	16.84 ± 3.16 ^c	18.96 ± 1.26 ^d	15.96 ± 0.91 ^b
C2	10.35 ± 1.50 ^a	12.82 ± 1.42 ^b	15.75 ± 0.92 ^d	13.18 ± 1.34 ^c
C3	11.37 ± 1.36 ^a	15.66 ± 1.85 ^c	17.78 ± 1.11 ^d	14.55 ± 0.90 ^b
CPX	36.12 ± 7.72 ^a	36.12 ± 7.72 ^a	36.12 ± 7.72 ^a	36.12 ± 7.73 ^a
CH	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a
SDW		0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a 0.01 ± 0.00 ^a

Key: C1 (Concoction 1), C2 (Concoction 2), C3 (Concoction 3), CPX (Ciprofloxacin), CH (Chloramphenicol), SDW (Sterile distilled water). Values with different superscripts in the same row are statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 4: Quantitative Phytochemical profile of concoction C1

Phytochemical	Concoction 1(mg/g)
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Total Phenol(mg/g)	576.69±0.01 ^a
Total Flavonoids(mg/g)	25.29±0.01 ^a
Saponin(mg/g)	418.18±0.01 ^b
Tannins(mg/g)	49.69±0.02 ^a
Terpenes(mg/g)	8.25±0.02 ^b

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study revealed that the HCs worked on exhibited antibacterial activity that is superior to most of the common conventional antibiotics tested except the fluoroquinolones against the isolated *Salmonella* species. More works however are recommended to know the mechanism of action of the HCs, determine the functional chemicals in them and also carry out *in vivo* studies on the HCs.

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